

Debunking Return Migration Policy Myths with the GAPs research

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	Policy Myth	Counter Evidence from GAPs Research	Link to Relevant GAPs output
1	Return is the end of a person's migration journey.	Return is just one moment in an ongoing journey, not an endpoint; returnees frequently want to remigrate and engage in circular mobility depending on opportunities.	WP1 framework paper https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/framework-paper-on-the-concepts-and-typologies-on-returns-combined-with-four-conceptual-notes WP7 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-in-mobile-trajectories-wp7
2	Forced and voluntary returns are completely different types of returns. Assisted voluntary return options are genuinely chosen by migrants.	The boundary between forced and voluntary return is often blurred, as both usually involve coercion. Assisted voluntary return is frequently a choice made under duress rather than a genuine preference. Migrants resort to assisted return because viable alternatives are systematically foreclosed because of prolonged legal insecurity, restricted access to work and services, the risk of detention, or the threat of forced removal.	Iraq human rights tradeoffs https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/political-and-human-rights-trade-offs-assisted-return-frameworks Article on coerced returns https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1369183X.2024.2371209
3	When armed conflict in the origin country ends, all displaced people from there are required to return and tend to go home.	Return decisions are shaped by a complex interplay of structural factors (conflict cessation, host-country conditions) and individuals' aspirations and capabilities. Displaced people may prioritise safety, dignity, and opportunity differently across locations, resulting in diverse outcomes, including delayed return, onward migration, circular mobility, or permanent settlement.	Dossier on return to Syria https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/research-dossier-on-syrian-refugee-return-dynamics WP8 comparative report (forthcoming)
4	Restrictive border controls and stringent asylum policies encourage migrants to return.	People continue to migrate despite increasing restrictions. Such barriers fail to deter movement and instead displace people towards longer, more clandestine and deadlier routes.	WP4 synthesis report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-governance-in-the-african-and-middle-eastern-regions WP7 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-in-mobile-trajectories-wp7

5	Detention is used as a last resort in removing rejected asylum seekers.	In practice, detention is widely deployed as a frontline tool in return procedures. Far from being exceptional, it is increasingly normalised. Detention is routinely used as a direct or indirect deterrence mechanism to discourage asylum claims and onward movement.	<p>Greece report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/irregularisation-in-greece-spatial-carceral-temporal-aspects</p> <p>WP2 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/legal-and-policy-infrastructures-of-returns-in-eu-comparative-report-wp2</p> <p>WP8 comparative report</p>
6	All administrative return decisions to return (or `removal orders`) respect migrants' rights.	Due to informality in administrative procedures, returns often involve human rights violations. Migrants are usually not sufficiently informed about their rights, available remedies, or the legal basis of return decisions. Removal orders and procedures do not always follow due process. And independent monitoring of return procedures is often not guaranteed.	<p>WP3 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-wp3-synthesis-report</p> <p>Iraq human rights tradeoffs https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/political-and-human-rights-trade-offs-assisted-return-frameworks</p> <p>Nigeria EU cooperation https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/research-digest-key-insights-on-nigeria-eu-migration-cooperation</p>
7	The EU level return rate is relatively low, ranging from 20 per cent to 30 per cent.	EU-level return rates are not clear. This is the result of data fragmentation and accuracy issues that obscure national-level realities. This opacity is deepened by policies that prioritise return rates over post-return sustainability and reintegration, potentially undermining effectiveness and triggering remigration cycles.	<p>Report on data https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/gaps-data-repository-on-return-guideline-data-samples-and-codebook</p> <p>Germany report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-in-germany</p>
8	Origin or transit countries are passive recipients of return agreements.	Origin and transit countries are active and strategic partners in migration diplomacy, extracting political or financial concessions and shaping the terms and implementation of return agreements. Their bargaining power is enabled by the EU's strong prioritisation of return. Return diplomacy thus reflects asymmetric and dynamic power relations rather than unilateral EU control. This leverage has also enabled transit countries to position themselves as gatekeepers and increasingly engage with the push for returns to origin countries.	<p>WP4 Synthesis Report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-governance-in-the-african-and-middle-eastern-regions</p> <p>Report on Turkey https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/eu-return-policies-the-case-of-turkey</p> <p>Report on Nigeria https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/challenges-and-opportunities-for-nigerian-migrants-from-north-africa-in-the-context-of-eu-policies</p> <p>Report on Libya https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/country-dossier-libya-return-migration-governance-african-middle-eastern-regions-role-of-eu</p>

9	Migrants' return home is usually smooth, and returnees can restart their lives thanks to support from their home countries or the IOM.	Returnees often find it difficult to return to the "home" they left behind. The support available to them is typically minimal and short-term, while they face demanding legal, economic, social and psychological conditions of reintegration.	<p>Report on Georgia https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-in-poland-and-georgia</p> <p>WP8 Report on Afghanistan https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/practices-and-experiences-of-returnees-in-afghanistan</p> <p>WP8 Report on Tunisia https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/postreturn-practices-experiences-of-returnees-tunisia</p>
10	Returns represent a threefold benefit for destination countries, origin countries, and migrants alike.	Returns carry both financial and social costs for destination countries. Meanwhile, origin countries often lack the capacity to absorb returnees because of their own structural issues. Many returnees have been forced to return and do not have sufficient resources to sustain themselves or to help develop their home countries.	<p>Cost of returns https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/cost-of-coerced-returns-in-germany</p> <p>WP8 comparative report</p>

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